

INVESTIGATION OF THE QUALITY OF SODIUM AND POTASSIUM SOAPS IN THE BLEND OF CASTOR OIL AND BEESWAX

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ABSTRACT

Background: Castor oil is one of the concerning plant oil that is produced from the kernel of castor plant that has the ingredients of ricinoleic acid and could make our skin become smooth. Beeswax is rich in basic soap production ingredients which include the fatty esters and acids. Different compound of soap making have different composition of fatty acids which are responsible for different properties of soaps made out of them.

Objectives: This study aims at soap made from the blend of beeswax and castor oil.

Methods: Different ratios of beeswax and castor oil were mixed to make soap blends with KOH and NaOH. Properties of these soap blend samples were analyzed to determine the best among the soap blend samples.

Results: The soaps have good qualities with respect to pH, foam ability, longevity, low free caustic alkali and total fatty matter, with the sodium soap of 1:1 of the soap blend having higher qualities. The FTIR spectroscopy of the samples were carried out and it shows the carboxylate bands present which indicate the good quality.

Conclusion: The study showed that soap made from blend of beeswax and castor oil is of good quality when compared to the soap made from single ingredient, the many desirable intrinsic qualities of castor oil and beeswax added to the qualities of the physicochemical properties tested in the soap blend thereby making it a very useful soap domestically and industrially.

Keywords: Castor oil, Bees wax, Oil extraction, Soap blends, Saponification

INTRODUCTION

Soaps are involved in human's day- to- day activities which include bathing, laundry and other cleansing activities. Soap is sodium or potassium salt of long-chain fatty acids, which is made by saponification reaction involving the hydrolysis of animal fats or vegetable oil with alkali, producing glycerol as the by-product. The soaps made from potassium alkali are usually soft or used as liquid soap while soaps from sodium alkali are hard. In addition to potassium and sodium salt, other metals such as calcium, magnesium and chromium are also used to produce metallic insoluble soap that are not used as cleaning agents but are used for other purposes. Other properties of the soap such as hardness are functions of the metallic element present in the salt (Antezana *et al.* 2015) A good soap is biodegradable when it does not contain chemicals that cannot break down into water, carbon dioxide and biological material after it has been discarded. Neither does it contain chemicals that can be harmful to the environment or cause undue destruction to the environment. The characteristics of soaps depend on the quality of the oil, and the amounts of the caustic soda and water used to make it. The speed of the reaction between the oil and the caustic soda is influenced by the

soda is influenced by the free fatty acid content of the oil, the heat of the components before mixing, and how vigorously the mixing is to be done. Free fatty acid contents, vigorous mixing, and heat speed up the given soap-making process. Soaps made from oils of low quality contain high non-saponifiable fatty acids (Sharma *et al.*, 2013).

Castor oil has long been used commercially as a highly renewable resource for the chemical industry. It is a vegetable oil obtained by pressing the seeds of the castor oil plant (*Ricinus communis L.*) that is mainly cultivated in Africa, South America, and India. The oil produced from this crop is considered to be of importance to the global specialty chemical industry because it is the only commercial source of hydroxylated fatty acid (Severino *et al.*, 2012). Castor oil is valuable due to the high content of ricinoleic acid, it has a unique fatty acid profile, with 85-95% ricinoleic acid, 2-6% oleic acid and 1-5% linoleic acid (Severino *et al.*, 2012). The hydroxyl functionality of ricinoleic acid makes the castor oil a natural polyol providing oxidative stability to the oil, and a relatively high shelf life compared to other oils by preventing peroxide formation (Severino *et al.*, 2012). Castor oil can be used as a basic ingredient in making soap because it has high saturated fat content, which is a major component in soap making (Severino *et al.*, 2012). Through different studies, it has been observed that soap from castor oil is very soft. Beeswax consists of an acid value of 17-24 (Adeyemi, 2022), saponification value of 89-103 (Adgaba, 2007) and an ester value of 72-79 (Bogdanov, 2004). It contains the complex mixture of 27 to 40% monoesters, 9 to 23% hydroxyl monoesters, 7 to 16% diesters, 3.9% hydroxyl diesters, 11 to 16% long chain hydrocarbons, 12 to 18% free fatty acids, 4 to 8% of other substances and less than 1% free fatty alcohols. Esters of the complex wax contain 15-hydroxyl palmitic acid or diols, which through their hydroxyl group, are linked to another fatty acid molecule (Puleo, 1991). Nevertheless, beeswax is composed of about 80% or more fatty esters and fatty acids

which are precursors for soap production. Beeswax is biodegradable and causes no harm to the environment; it gives off a pleasant smell, and yellow in colour (Adeyemi, 2022). It has also been reported to show an antimicrobial effectiveness against the growth of microorganisms such as *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albican* (Fratini, *et al.*, 2016). These characteristics are expected to make beeswax a good candidate in soap making. Although, not much research has been done on soap making from beeswax, it gives a harder bar of soap.

Castor oil soaps are usually very soft which may lead to wastage on use, it is also very reactive to surfaces such as skin. Beeswax soaps on the other hand are hard, less foaming and have high longevity. A blend of castor oil and beeswax is expected to give better quality soap than the individual ingredient. Hence, the study is aim at investigating the quality of sodium and potassium soaps made from the blend of castor oil and beeswax.

Materials and Methodology

Materials

Castor seed and Honeycomb was obtained from a farmer and a beekeeper in Ondo-City, Ondo State, Nigeria. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Sample preparation

The preparation of the seeds involves removing the seeds from the shell manually, and cleaning any foreign matter introduced during sun drying and any unshelled seeds. The seeds were properly dried using electric oven set at 80°C for 48hours. The dried seed samples were powdered using mortar and pestle to reduce the sizes so as to increase the interfacial area between the solvent and the powdered seeds.

2.2.2 Extraction of the castor oil

700ml of n-hexane was poured into the round bottom flask. 100g of powdered castor seeds was placed in the thimble and inserted in the center of the Soxhlet extractor. The extractor was set at a heating temperature between 70-75°C when the solvent was boiling; the vapour rises through the vertical tube into the

condenser at the top. The liquid condensate drips into the filter paper thimble in the center which contains the solid sample to be extracted. The extract sips through the pores of the thimble and fills the siphon tube where it flows back down into the round bottom flask. This was allowed for some minutes after which the sample was removed from the tube, dried in the oven, cooled in the desiccator and weighed to determine the amount of oil extracted. The extracted oil mixed with solvent was heated at the end of the extraction to recover the solvent from the oil (Adeyemi, 2022). The solvent free oil was then refined for further use.

2.2.3 Castor oil refining

The refining process steps include degumming, neutralization, bleaching, and deodorization. The oil is degummed by adding hot water to the oil, allowing the mixture to sit, and finally the aqueous layer is removed. Following the degumming step, sodium hydroxide was added for neutralization. The base was removed using hot water, and separation between the aqueous layer and oil allows the removal of the water layer. Neutralization is followed by bleaching to remove colour, remaining phospholipids, and any leftover oxidation products. The castor oil was then deodorized to remove any odour from the oil (Bankole, 2007).

Extraction of beeswax from honeycomb

The beeswax was extracted over hot water, the wax combs was soaked in water for several hours and washed intermittently so as to remove water soluble material from the combs, and this is to prevent the melted wax from absorbing some impurities and colouration. After this, combs were melted over boiling water. The melted wax floats on the surface and strained along with boiling water through wet cloth to remove bees and other foreign material present in combs. After cooling at room temperature, the wax cake was formed and removed from the surface of water. The process was continuously repeated (Adeyemi, 2022).

2.2.5 Preparation of the soap

100g of NaOH was weighed, dissolved and made up to mark in a 1000ml standard volumetric flask to prepare a 2M NaOH solution. 10g of the castor oil and the beeswax were measured into a stainless container. It was warmed in order to give homogeneity to the raw samples and to also quicken the reaction between the alkali and the fat. The caustic soda was poured gradually into the stainless container and stirred gently using a stirring rod in one direction to enhance thorough mixing of the solution. The stainless container was insulated with pieces of cloths to prevent the fat from hardening before the soap mix properly. The heating was done at 65-70°C on a hotplate. The cooking continued until the liquid system forms a solid material upon further addition of the NaOH solution, leaving out unreacted alkali solution. The heating source was then withdrawn and the whole system was allowed to stand for 30 minutes. Thereafter, the soapy solid material was rinsed with distilled water to remove excess NaOH. The soap was then filtered to remove most of the liquid still present. The products obtained were dried to constant weight in an oven at 80°C. The process was repeated with 2M KOH solution, and different mass ratio of beeswax and castor oil.

2.2.6 Determination of Physical and Chemical Properties of the Beeswax, castor oil and Soap Samples

The chemical and physical parameters determined includes:

2.2.6.1 Saponification value: 2g of the extracted oil was placed in a conical flask to which 25ml of ethanoic potassium hydroxide (1M) was added and the mixture was allowed to boil gently for 60 minutes with shaking at 5 minutes intervals. Two drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added to the warm solution and then titrated with 0.5M HCl. The end point was reached when the pink colour of the indicator disappeared. The same procedure was repeated for the blank.

The equation below describes the calculation for:

$$SV = \frac{(B-S) \times M \times 56.1}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

Where B is the volume of the titrant for the blank (ml), S is the volume of the titrant for

the sample, and M is the molarity of HCl and 56.1 is the molecular weight of KOH

2.2.6.2 Acid value: To determine the acid value (AV) of the beeswax and castor oil, different ratios of both sample was dissolved in 50ml neutralized 99% methanol and warm until melted. The resulting solution was titrated against 0.5M methanoic KOH using phenolphthalein indicator until a permanent, faint pink color was obtained. The equation below was used to obtain the free fatty acid value.

$$AV = \frac{\text{titre value(ml)} \times M \times 56.1}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

Where M is the molarity of KOH solution. The difference between the SV and AV gave the ester value.

2.2.6.3 Iodine value: The iodine values (IV) of different ratios of beeswax and castor oil samples were determined using the method described by (AOAC, 1984) with slight modification. Different ratios of beeswax and castor oil samples were dissolved in 30ml CHCl₃ followed by the addition of 25ml of 25% ICl solution (in glacial acetic acid). The mixture was left in the dark for 45 minutes, followed by the addition of 25ml of 10% KI solution and 100ml distilled water. The resulting solution was titrated against 0.1 M Na₂S₂O₃ solution till the colour becomes pale yellow after which 2ml of starch solution was added as indicator and the titration continued until the blue colour disappeared. The procedure was repeated for the prepared soaps. Blank determination was also carried out alongside the samples. The equation below shows how the IV was calculated:

$$IV = \frac{(B-S) \times M \times 126.9 \times 10^{-1}}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

Where B is the volume of the titrant for the blank (ml), S is the volume of the titrant for the sample, M is the molarity of Na₂S₂O₃ and 126.9 is the molecular weight of iodine.

2.2.6.3 Peroxide value

The peroxide value (PV) of the beeswax and castor oil samples was determined by dissolving different ratios of beeswax and castor oil samples in 30ml chloroform/glacial acetic acid

mixture (2:3 V/V). 1mL of freshly prepared saturated KI solution was added followed by 30 ml distilled water, shaken and titrated slowly with 0.01M Na₂S₂O₃ till the colour changes to pale yellow. Then 0.5ml of 1% starch indicator was added and the titration continues until the blue colour disappears. The procedure was repeated for the blank solution. The equation below shows how PV was calculated:

$$PV = \frac{(S-B) \times M \times 1000}{\text{Weight of sample}}$$

Where B is the volume of the titrant for the blank (ml), S is the volume of the titrant for the sample; M is the molarity of Na₂S₂O₃.

2.2.6.4 pH value:

The pH values of the soap samples were determined by dissolving 2g of the soap in 20ml distilled water (10% soap solution) and shaken properly (Dalen and Mamza, 2009). The resulting soap suspension was allowed to stay for 15 hours before the pH meter (Hanna Instrument) was inserted into small plastic tubes containing the soap suspension, and the readings was recorded. The pH meter was calibrated using a buffer solution of pH 6.86 and 10.01 before use on the soap solution.

2.2.6.5 Moisture content:

The soap's moisture content was determined by heating 5g of the soap sample in crucible at 103°C in an oven to a constant mass. The equation below was used in calculating the percentage moisture content:

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{WS_b - WS_a}{WS_a} \times 100$$

Where, WS_a is the weight of the soap sample after drying, WS_b is the weight of soap sample before drying.

2.2.6.6 Test for cleaning effectiveness

The cleaning effectiveness of the prepared soaps was examined and compared with those of commercial laundry and toilet soaps. Four strips of filter paper were stained with 2 drops of groundnut oil, and they were therefore immersed in the different tubes, each contained 2% of a soap solution in tap water. The four

tubes were shaken vigorously for 3 minutes in a centrifuge. The filter papers was removed and rinsed with enough tap water and their levels of cleanliness was observed.

2.2.6.7 Foaming power and foam stability

50ml of each of different concentrations of the prepared soaps solutions was shaken vigorously in a 250ml measuring cylinder for 1 minute and the foam volumes was noted after 1 minute of settlement.

For foam stability, 50ml each of 4% soap solutions was transferred into a 250ml measuring cylinder. The mixture was shaken vigorously for about 1 minute. The foams generated were allowed to settle and their levels were noted after 1, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 minutes. The foam stability was expressed as a ratio of the foam volume V_t at time t in minute to that at 1 minute V_o , (V_t/V_o). For comparison, the process was repeated for two commercial toilet and one commercial laundry soaps.

2.2.6.8 Free caustic alkali:

The methods used by Ashrafy *et al.* (2016), Boday *et al.* (2017) and Legesse (2020) were modified and adopted. 2.5g of each of the soap was dissolved in warmed 40ml ethanol. Two drops of phenolphthalein indicator and 10ml of 20% $BaCl_2$ was added to each soap solution. The resulting solutions were titrated against 0.05M H_2SO_4 till it gives colourless solutions. The equation below was used to obtain the free caustic alkali (FCA) value.

$$FCA = \frac{0.31}{W} \times V_A$$

3.0 Results and Discussion.

3.1 Percentage Yield of Castor Oil

Percentage Yield of extracted oil was calculated using the following formula.

$$\text{percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Actual yield}}{\text{Theoretical yield}} \times 100\%$$

Mass of castor seed before extraction = theoretical yield = 316g,

Mass of castor oil after extraction = actual yield = 153g:

$$\% \text{ yield} = \frac{153 \text{ g}}{316 \text{ g}} \times 100\% = 48 \%$$

3.2 Physicochemical properties of beeswax, castor oil, and soap blend samples

The soaps blend produced lather well and gave pleasant smell. The potassium soap gave better solubility and foaming qualities than the sodium soap. Moreover, all the soaps have good cleansing property. The pH values of the soap blend for 1:1 NaOH and 1:2 NaOH falls in the lower limit of pH range (9.0 – 10) of most commercial soaps (Tarun *et al.*, 2014), except for the 1:1 KOH and 1:2 KOH soap blends with values 11.45 and 10.97. High pH value of soap is an indication of incomplete hydrolysis from the saponification reaction. However, the low pH observed in NaOH soap blend in this study maybe due to complete hydrolysis.

Iodine value (IV):

The iodine value is a measure of the unsaturation of a fat or oil, expressed in grams of iodine that can be absorbed by 100 grams of the sample. Low iodine numbers was observed in all soap samples that suggests low degree of unsaturation, which corresponds to high hardness and good longevity in the soap samples as shown in Table 1, Low iodine value soaps, are more stable and show resistant to oxidation (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2017). Free caustic alkali refers to the amount of unreacted or excess caustic alkali that remains in soap after the saponification process. It is the amount of alkali free to counter and avert the soap from becoming oily. In this study, the free caustic alkalis obtained were 0.062% (1:1 sodium soap) and 0.334% (1:1 potassium soap), 0.421% (1:2 sodium soap) and 0.412% (1:2 potassium soap). This indicates that the ratio 1:1 sodium soap blend has the least free alkali value. Excess level of free caustic alkali can be irritating or corrosive to the eyes and skin (Ashrafy *et al.*, 2016). The observed values showed that the ratio 1:1 sodium soap blend is the best prepared soap and safe to use among the other prepared soaps blend. Saponification value is the measure of the average molecular weight of a fat or oil, required to saponify one gram of the sample. The long chain fatty acids found in fats have low saponification value because they have a relatively fewer number of carboxylic functional groups per unit mass of the fat and therefore high molecular weight. Oils with high saponification values such as castor oil (183) are

Table 1: Physiochemical properties of beeswax, castor oil and the soap blend samples

Parameters			Soap blends (castor oil+ beeswax)			
	Beeswax	Castor oil	1:1 NaOH	1:1 KOH	1:2 NaOH	1:2 KOH
Color	Yellow	Yellow	Cream	Cream	Cream	Cream
Saponification	96	183	-	-	-	-
Acid value	19.64	5.61	-	-	-	-
Ester value	76.36	177.39	-	-	-	-
Peroxide value	8	3	-	-	-	-
pH	-	-	9.96	11.45	9.93	10.17
Solubility	Insoluble	Insoluble	Fair	Moderate	Moderate	Good
Foaming ability	-	-	Good	Good	Good	Good
Foam stability	-	-	Moderate	Good	Poor	Moderate
Iodine value	7.8	10.97	8.30	8.57	8.44	7.80
Moisture content (%)	-	-	1.00	1.56	3.12	1.56
Hardness	Hard	Oily	Mildly hard	Very soft	Hard	Soft
Cleansing power	-	-	Good	Fair	Good	Good
Longevity	-	-	Good	Good	Good	Good
Free caustic alkali	-	-	0.0620	0.3348	0.4216	0.4216

better used in soap making (Abayeh *et al.*, 1998). When castor oil is blended with beeswax, the saponification number of the soap blend is higher than that of castor oil, which makes it a better quality soaps. The foaming ability and stability gave a moderate to good performance except for 1:2 NaOH soap blend, and all the soap blend show a good solubility in water, likewise displayed a good cleansing properties.

3.3 Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The Fourier Transformed infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy spectral for the castor oil and the prepared blend soaps are shown in Figures 1 (A-E) and Figure 1 (F) for beeswax. Soap is a process of saponification, which involves reacting the oil with an alkaline substance (sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide) (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2012). The soap contains various components, like fatty acids, glycerin, and other byproducts of saponification process. The major functional groups and their corresponding peaks observed in the FTIR spectrum present in the castor oil, beeswax and the soaps from the blend of bees-

wax and castor oil are: the carboxylic acid functional group (-COOH) which is prominent in all the FTIR spectrum. The typical peak for carboxylic acids appears in the range of 1700-1750 cm^{-1} , indicating the stretching vibration of the C=O bond. Hydroxyl Groups (-OH), were also found in castor oil, beeswax and in all the blend soaps. The stretching vibration of the hydroxyl group produces a broad peaks around 3350-3472 cm^{-1} in the FTIR spectrum. The characteristic peaks related to aliphatic chains were also observed in the FTIR spectrum. The stretching vibration of C-H bonds in alkanes typically results in peaks around 2850-3000 cm^{-1} in all the samples which may likely be derived from the fatty acids. Other byproducts from the saponification process which may be present in the soap blend and can introduce additional functional groups in the FTIR spectrum are esters or amides (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2012). The peaks around 1735-1750 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching) and 1150-1300 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching) indicates the presence of esters which is an indication that there is complete saponification reactions. Amides: The presence of amides exhibit the characteristic peaks around 1638-1680 cm^{-1}

(C=O stretching) and $3200-3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N-H stretching). Similarly, bands at around $1190-1016$ and 719 cm^{-1} maybe be associated to C-O stretch, and long-chain (CH_2) group in the finger print region.

Figure 1 (A): FTIR Spectral of Ratio 1:1 KOH Prepared Soap

Figure 1 (B): FTIR Spectral of Ratio 1:1 NaOH Prepared Soap

Figure 1 (C): FTIR Spectral of Ratio 1:2 KOH Prepared Soap

Figure 1 (D): FTIR Spectral of Ratio 1:2 NaOH Prepared Soap

Figure 1(E): FTIR Spectral of the Castor Oil

Figure 1(F): FTIR Spectral of Beeswax (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2021)

Conclusions

Soaps blend prepared from beeswax and castor oil at different ratio gave a successful saponification which was observed in the FTIR spectra of the Na and K soaps. The beeswax and castor oil soaps have good qualities with respect to pH, foaming ability, longevity and hardness. The best blend was found out to be 1:1 NaOH prepared soap. It had excellent lathering as well as cleansing power, the lowest free caustic alkali value of 0.062 and iodine number of 8.30.

This research shows that soap made from blend of beeswax and castor oil is of good quality

when compared to the soap made from single ingredient, the many desirable intrinsic qualities of castor oil and beeswax added to the qualities of the physicochemical properties tested in the soap blend thereby making it a very useful soap domestically and industrially.

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